

Modelling and Forecasting Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) with Hybrid ARIMA-RBF Model

Babafemi Daniel Ogunbona^{1*}, Bala, U. F.² and Aliyu Baba Masaya³

¹*Department of Mathematics, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo*

²*Department of Computer Science, Usman Danfodiyo University, Sokoto*

³*Department of Computer Science, Yobe State University*

*Correspondence Author email: ogunbonabd@aceondo.edu.ng

ABSTRACT A nation's GDP is a crucial indicator of economic development and income levels. This study examines a hybrid model combining Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and Radial Basis Function (RBF) to best fit Nigeria's annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) data from 1960 to 2022. The series was tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and was found to be stationary at the second differencing. The ARIMA (3, 2, 1) model was identified as the suitable ARIMA configuration. Thereafter, RBF was used to model the nonlinearity in the residuals of the selected ARIMA. The best RBF model was the one consisting of one input with one neuron, one hidden layer with ten neurons and one output layer with one neuron $N^{(1,10,1)}$. The results of the out-of-sample forecasted period showed that hybrid ARIMA-RBF outperformed the standalone ARIMA model.

KEYWORDS: Forecasting, GDP, Hybrid ARIMA-RBF. Modelling

I. INTRODUCTION

Time series forecasting plays a crucial role in economics and finance, providing valuable insights into future trends and enabling informed decision-making. One essential economic indicator that has garnered much interest among researchers and practitioners is the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The gross domestic product (GDP) is a crucial economic indicator that measures the total value of goods and services produced within the borders of a country over a specific period. It serves as a measure of overall health and growth rate of an economy [1]. However, accurately predicting GDP remains a challenging task due to its complex and volatile nature, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. In response to this challenge, advanced statistical models such as Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) have been widely used for time series forecasting, including GDP forecasting. Additionally, the Radial Basis Function (RBF) neural network model has shown promising results in improving the accuracy of GDP forecasts. The ARIMA model, originally proposed by [2], integrates autoregression, differencing, and moving average components to identify patterns and dependencies within a time series. Over the years, it has become one of the most commonly used tools for univariate time series forecasting across various fields, including economics and finance [3]. Despite its widespread use, some authors argue that traditional statistical models like ARIMA might not adequately account for nonlinearities present in real-world data [4]. On the other hand, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), specifically Radial Basis Function (RBF), offers an alternative approach to time series forecasting based on computational algorithms inspired by biological neuronal networks [5]. ANNs have shown promising results when applied to financial and economic datasets, capturing complex relationships and nonlinear dynamics inherent in such systems [6]. Nevertheless, concerns about overfitting and interpretability issues persist, prompting further investigation into the practical implications of using MLPs for GDP forecasting in the Nigerian context. In the context of Nigeria, a country with a rapidly growing economy and significant economic challenges, accurate modelling and forecasting of GDP is essential for sustainable economic development. Nigeria's GDP has experienced fluctuations due to various factors such as oil price volatility, political instability, and economic policies. This study aims to build on existing research and provide a robust methodology for forecasting Nigeria's GDP with enhanced accuracy and reliability by combining the strengths of ARIMA in capturing time series patterns and

RBF in handling nonlinear relationships. This model is expected to provide more accurate predictions of Nigeria's economic performance. The paper consists of four sections. The introduction section motivates the writing of the article. The next section describes the model methodology. The third section presents the analysis and discussion of results, and the final section summarizes the research in the conclusion.

II. RELATED WORKS

In economic research, the integration of different forecasting models has proven to be highly effective in improving the accuracy of predictions for various indicators, including GDP. This study explores the hybridization of Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) and Radial Basis Function (RBF) networks to model and forecast Nigeria's GDP. Building on the success of previous studies that utilized combined models, this research aims to capture the intricate patterns in Nigeria's economic data. For instance, [7] investigated the impact of real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on unemployment in Nigeria, analyzing data from 1977 to 2011 to explore both long-term and short-term relationships between real GDP and unemployment, with unemployment as the dependent variable. Their findings indicated a positive relationship between unemployment and real GDP in Nigeria in both the short and long run, concluding that real GDP growth contributes to unemployment in Nigeria. Another study, [8], analyzed Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) over a fifty-three-year period (1960-2012) using time series trend analysis. Their results demonstrated that Nigeria experienced substantial economic growth during this period. [9] utilized an ARIMA-RBF model to forecast the monthly incidence of hand-foot-mouth disease (HFMD) in China from January 2008 to December 2014, achieving improved forecasting accuracy compared to standalone ARIMA or RBF models. [10] applied a similar ARIMA-RBF approach to forecast Nigeria's quarterly GDP from 2009 to 2015, demonstrating higher accuracy than traditional ARIMA or RBF models alone. In another study, [11] investigated the sectoral contributions to Nigeria's GDP from 1970 to 2012 using trend analysis graphs, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis, finding that various sectors (agriculture, petroleum, education, health, and telecommunications) contributed to GDP growth at different rates. [12] compared the Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model (SARIMA) with the Bilinear Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model (BARIMA) for analyzing Nigeria's GDP using quarterly data from the first quarter of 1993 to the fourth quarter of 2012, recommending BARIMA due to its lower AIC. Similarly, [13] employed Fourier time series analysis to model Nigeria's GDP from 2005 to 2015, highlighting the method's effectiveness in capturing GDP trends through a computational algorithm that aided estimation. Additionally, [14] used ARIMA to analyze annual GDP data for Nigeria from 1981 to 2019, identifying ARIMA (1, 2, 1) as the appropriate model. [15] focused on clustering Nigeria's GDP components to better understand their contributions, pinpointing crude oil as a key economic driver. [16] compared various multivariate time series models, including MLRM, VARM, and MARDLM, for forecasting Nigeria's GDP, finding VARM to be the most accurate and emphasizing crude oil's significance in GDP prediction. Furthermore, [17] analyzed the contributions of different sectors to Nigeria's GDP over 33 years using regression and ARIMA models, concluding that the service sector had the most significant impact, while the agricultural sector's contribution was minimal. [18] applied an n-variable regression model to assess the relationship between GDP and major economic sectors in Nepal, highlighting the critical roles of agriculture, industry, and services. Finally, [19] developed a dynamic regression model to analyze Nigeria's GDP over 50 years, recommending economic diversification beyond crude oil.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. ARIMA MODELS

The ARIMA model was introduced by Box and Jenkins in 1976, The ARIMA models are generated from the autoregressive models and the moving averages models, the differences for the time series are taken to convert the non-stationary series into a stationary series which is called the degree of integrated (d) and the model symbolizes by ARIMA (p, d, q). The ARIMA models can be expressed using the backshift operator (B) as follows:

$$(1 - \phi_1 B - \phi_2 B^2 - \dots - \phi_p B^p)(1 - B)^d y_t = c + (1 + \theta_1 B + \theta_2 B^2 + \dots + \theta_q B^q) \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

In a more compact form is:

$$\phi_p(B)(1 - B)^d y_t = c + \theta_q(B) \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

where, B is the backshift operator, y_t is the value of the time series at time t , ϕ_i are the autoregressive coefficients, θ_j are the moving average coefficients, d the degree of differencing and ε_t is the error term at time t .

B. RADIAL BASES FUNCTION (RBF)

RBF, short for Radial Basis Function, represents a type of artificial neural network (ANN). An RBF network is a feed-forward neural network consisting of multiple interconnected layers of artificial neurons. Its basic structure comprises three layers: the input layer receives the data, the hidden layer processes it through neurons with nonlinear activation functions, and the output layer generates the predictions. The hidden layer in RBF networks is characterized by neurons with radial symmetry transfer functions centered around specific points (Mackey, 1997). Figure 1 illustrates a typical RBF network.

Figure 1: Typical RBF network

The output of the net is given by the following expression:

$$F(\vec{x}, \Phi, w) = \sum_{i=1}^m \phi_i(\vec{x}) \cdot w_i \quad (3)$$

where $\Phi = \{\phi_i : i=1, 2, \dots, m\}$ are the basis functions set and w_i are the associated weights for every Radial Basis Function (RBF). The basis function ϕ can be calculated as a Gaussian function using the following expression:

$$\phi_1(\vec{x}, \vec{c}, r) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|\vec{x} - \vec{c}\|^2}{r}\right) \quad (4)$$

where \vec{c} is the central point of the function ϕ , r is its radius and \vec{x} is the input vector.

IV. Results and Discussion

A. DATA

The data for this study includes the annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Nigeria from 1960 to 2022, sourced from the World Bank database website (<http://www.factfish.com/statistic-country/nigeria/grossdomesticproduct>). The data were divided into training set (44 data points) and test set (last 19 data points). The data was first made stationary. ARIMA model was first used to estimate the linear part of the stationary data. Secondly, residuals obtained from the selected ARIMA model were estimated by the RBF model. Lastly, forecasts of last 19 months were obtained using the proposed hybrid method.

Figure 2: Time Plot of Original GDP Series

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for GDP shows p-value of $0.4122 > 0.05$ which means that the original series is non-stationary.

Figure 3: Time Plot of the Second Differencing of GDP Series

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for GDP shows p-value of $8.171e-011 < 0.05$ which means that the original series is stationary.

Figure 4: ACF and PACF Plots of the Second Differencing of GDP Series

From the ACF and PACF in figure 3, we have ARIMA (1, 2, 1) and ARIMA (3, 2, 1). The selection procedure revealed the results in table 1 below:

Table 1: Result of ARIMA Model Selection for GDP

Model	AIC	SIC	HQIC
ARIMA (1, 2, 1)	2111.642	2118.397	2114.084
ARIMA (3, 2, 1)	2105.029	2115.163	2108.693

Source: Results of Data Processing using Microsoft Excel

The above table shows that ARIMA (3, 2, 1) lower AIC, HQC and SIC than ARIMA (1, 2, 1). Hence, ARIMA (3, 2, 1) was selected.

B. ARIMA ((3,2,1) MODEL ESTIMATION

After the best model has been chosen, the parameters of the model are estimated. The results of this estimate (with residual test for normality) are shown in the table below:

Table 2: Result of ARIMA (3,2,1) Model Estimation for GDP

Parameter	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z	P-value
Constant	8.04E+07	2.34E+08	0.3428	0.7317
Phi_1	-1.06195	0.152019	-6.986	2.84e-012 ***
phi_2	0.721335	0.204006	-3.536	0.0004 ***
phi_3	-0.361375	0.163135	-2.215	0.0267 **
theta_1	-1.00000	0.0687182	-14.55	5.66e-048 ***

Source: Results of Data Processing using Microsoft Excel

Table 2 shows that all the parameters of ARIMA (3,2,1) are significant at 5% significance level which shows that the selected ARIMA is a good fit for Nigeria’s GDP.

C. OUT-OF-SAMPLE FORECASTS

The GDP data spanning sixty-three years (1960-2022) was analyzed and modeled using ARIMA and then compared with results obtained from a hybrid ARIMA-RBF model.

Table 3: Result of forecast for GDP using ARIMA and ARIMA-RBF

YEAR	ACTUAL	ARIMA	ARIMA-RBF
2004	1.35765E+11	1.08E+11	1.52986E+11
2005	1.75671E+11	1.07E+11	1.61614E+11
2006	2.38455E+11	1.09E+11	2.38455E+11
2007	2.78261E+11	1.13E+11	3.17463E+11
2008	3.39476E+11	1.17E+11	3.17951E+11
2009	2.95009E+11	1.22E+11	3.17803E+11
2010	3.6699E+11	1.25E+11	3.18645E+11
2011	4.14467E+11	1.29E+11	3.31096E+11
2012	4.63971E+11	1.33E+11	3.17951E+11
2013	5.20117E+11	1.37E+11	3.17951E+11
2014	5.74184E+11	1.41E+11	3.17951E+11
2015	4.93027E+11	1.45E+11	3.17951E+11
2016	4.04649E+11	1.49E+11	4.00816E+11
2017	3.75746E+11	1.53E+11	3.17951E+11
2018	4.21739E+11	1.57E+11	4.32963E+11
2019	4.74517E+11	1.61E+11	3.17951E+11

2020	4.32199E+11	1.66E+11	4.33794E+11
2021	4.40839E+11	1.70E+11	4.30554E+11
2022	4.72625E+11	1.75E+11	3.17963E+11

Source: Results of Data Processing using Microsoft Excel

The empirical findings indicate that the hybrid model offers superior forecasting accuracy compared to the traditional Box-Jenkins ARIMA method. Point forecasts generated by both ARIMA and ARIMA-RBF algorithms are presented in Table 3.

Table 4: Comparison of Out-of-sample Forecasting Performance

Forecast Evaluation Statistics	ARIMA	ARIMA-RBF
Mean Square Error	7.11398E+22	1.17276E+22
Root Mean Square Error	2.6672E+11	1.08294E+11
Mean Absolute % Error	61.09441789	16.84307594

Source: Results of Data Processing using Microsoft Excel

As shown in Table 4, the predictions from the hybrid model are more precise than those from the ARIMA model, as evidenced by lower metrics across the board.

Figure 5: Structure of the Selected RBF for Hybrid Model

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results

V. Conclusion

In this paper, Nigeria’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has been modeled using ARIMA and hybrid ARIMA-RBF models. ARIMA was used to model the linear patterns in the series yielding ARIMA (3, 2, 1) as an appropriate ARIMA model. Thereafter, RBF was used to model the nonlinearity in the residuals of the selected ARIMA. The best RBF model was the one consisting of one input with one neuron, one hidden layer with ten neurons and one output layer with one neuron N (1,10,1). The results of the out-of-sample forecasted period showed that hybrid ARIMA-RBF outperformed the standalone ARIMA model.

References

- [1] World Bank. World Development Indicators: GDP - Current US\$, 2021, Accessed on: April 23, 2024, [Online] Available: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?locations=NG> ,
- [2] G. E. P. Box and G. M. Jenkins “Time Series Analysis: Forecasting and Control,” Holden Day, 1976.
- [3] S. Aydin, “Time Series Analysis and Some Applications in Medical Research,” *Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Studies*, 31-36, 2022, DOI: 10.32996/jmss. www.al-kindipublisher.com/index.php/jmss.
- [4] Y. Zhang, B. D. Patuwo, and C. C. Hu, “Time series forecasting by combining artificial neural network and ARIMA models,” *Computers & Operations Research*, 30(3), 361-377, 2003.
- [5] S. Haykin, “Nonlinear Systems and Neural Networks,” Macmillan College Publishing Company, 1994.
- [6] L. Barbaglia, *et al.*, “Data Science for Economics and Finance,” 16, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66891-4>.
- [7] S. Buba, and S. Ishak, “An Analysis of the Effect of Real Gross Domestic Product on Unemployment in Nigeria: (An ARDL- Approach),” *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(14), 7-13, 2014, <http://www.iiste.org>.
- [8] D. O. Onuoha *et al.*, “Analysis of The Gross Domestic Product (G.D.P) of Nigeria: 1960-2012,” *West African Journal of Industrial & Academic Research*, 14(1), 2015.
- [9] Y. B. Wang, *et al.*, “Comparison on predictive capacity and fitting efficiency of ARIMA,RBF and ARIMA-RBF combination model for incidence of hand-foot-mouth disease[J],” *Chinese Journal of Public Health*, 33(5), 760-763, 2017, DOI: 10.11847/zgggws2017-33-05-1.
- [10] S. Adebisi, *et al.*, “Forecasting Nigerian quarterly real GDP using autoregressive integrated moving average radial basis function network model.” *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 5(6), 1347-1358, 2017.
- [11] C. R. Okezie, and O. D. Ihebuzoaju, “Sectoral Contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria Economy (1970 – 2012),” *Scientific Papers Series Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development*, 17(3), 231-238, 2017.
- [12] A. E. Usoro, “Modelling of Nigeria Gross Domestic Product Using Seasonal and Bilinear Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Models,” *Journal of Statistical and Econometric Methods*, 7(2), 1-21, 2018.
- [13] I. B. Lekara-Bayo, and E. Etuk, “28 Fourier Time Series Analysis of Nigeria Gross Domestic Product,” *International Journal of Management Studies, Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 4(3), 28-43, 2019.
- [14] E. Y. Atanu *et al.* “ARIMA Model for Gross Domestic Product (GDP): Evidence from Nigeria,” *Archives of Current Research International*, 20(7), 49-69, 2020.
- [15] E. H. Etuk, “Cluster analysis of Nigerian real GDP,” *Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 2020.
- [16] U. Anthony and E. Udoh, “Multivariate Time Series Modelling of Nigerian Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Some Macroeconomic Variables,” *African Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Studies*, 4(3), 12-31, 2021.
- [17] G. E. Kenneth and I. P. Onyedikachi, “On the Contribution of Some Economic Sectors to Nigeria Gross Domestic Product,” *Sch Bull*, 7(3), 49-59, 2021.
- [18] K. C. Krishna and K. M Anjay, “Analysis of GDP using the n-variable Regression Model,” *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 6(1), 170-175, 2021.
- [19] O. T. Oki, and O. S. Makinde, “Statistical Analysis of Nigeria Gross Domestic Products,” *Ann. Appl. Sci.*, 7(2), 1-4, 2021.